

‘AN IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE HOSPITALITY ENTREPRENEURSHIP’

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ABSTRACT

To ensure a successful transformation, appropriate security practices must be integrated from the beginning. Additionally, one of the factors that enables digital transformation with the help of engaging consumers, empowering employees, and optimizing processes, services, and goods. A hotel needs to have IT assistance for any technological concerns in addition to collaborating with third parties like Uber or Netflix, Zomato, Ola. The app should also be promoted to increase usage and educate guests about the technology. Initially new technology was embraced by the hospitality sector. Gradually digitalization has impacted this industry and in the post-COVID future, it is expected to have even more substantial effects which is based on growth. Due to digitalization hospitality will drastically change in the future. Many hospitality businesses are expanding their online offerings and enabling virtual visits for the places like museums, galleries, exhibitions, castles, zoos, aquariums, locations in an effort to stay relevant. An entrepreneur of hospitality sector will be even more dependent on digitization and emerging technology in the future.

KEYWORDS: Digital, Business, Invention, Customers

INTRODUCTION

Radical change isn't just with regards to innovation venture, yet refers to the manners in which relations reconstruct themselves to adjust and modify corporate culture to engage developments that influence innovation before take their managements advanced than ever of growth. The word 'advanced change' was begat in the last part of the 1990s to describe when a customer first was interfacing with an organization through a place or other electronic channel. As the network advanced administrations initiated to companion all series and devices into network places. (Huijbens, (2019)) Basically each group takes through a progressive alteration to number out to use evidence, grip skill, grow their revenue, and recover. Progressive alteration at its midpoint refers to the capacity of a connotation to alteration its method to contract by novelty, persons, and series to affect business implementation and take worth to procurers. As one master portrays, "Computerized alteration shuts the hut between what advanced clients as of now expect and what simple organizations really convey."

Break with the past in the hotel industry requires to take a lead in the digital transformation undertakes the additional value of the businesses. (Ferreira J. J., (2017))It can be done through the partnerships with techno savvy businesses incorporation which can be identify the challenges regarding the digitalization business. This modification is essential for the start-ups as well as the corporates for their betterment.

Innovative entrepreneurs are always trying for to adopt new technology for the business development and customer needs. Entrepreneurs has developed their own app for easy transaction for their business.

Digital transformation has a progressive influence on business enactment, probably the business is capable to progress its effectiveness and endorse its development possible complete challenging digital transformation. The results show that digital transformation is a task that every company cannot avoid due to: The company needs to adapt to its potential to fit into a broadly established business activity model and use it as a business development strategy. (Ferreira, (2017))

Building the right bridges (between the front end and posterior workplace, data from "objects" and choices, people, groups, tools, many companies in ecosystems, etc.) in the purpose of that excursion is essential to flourish. The digital transformation lineup is an excursion with several linked middle aims, in the finish, endeavoring to optimistic fractious functional methods, separations, and the commercial ecosystem of a hyper-connected age.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The mindset of Entrepreneurs to creation of new things. Ready to accept innovative things with the risk. Rogers (2003), acceptance is a choice of "complete usage of an invention as the finest sequence of performance offered" and denunciation is a choice "not to accept an invention" (p. 177). Rogers describes dispersal as "the procedure in which an invention is connected full certain networks ended time amongst the memberships of a communal scheme"

As stated in this definition, invention, communication networks, period, and communal system are the four important gears of the dispersal of inventions.

Now a days consumer behavior is highly influenced by the online border and has a significant importance. The two groups namely the Gen Z and the Millennials are very much influenced and attracted by the technology as they grow and expand in their business carriers and are highly techno friendly (Euromonitor, 2015). When the concern is about the hospitality sector there has been a various new inventions and innovations in the last two spans. Now the tourists can analyze in advance in respect to the location and place to stay and the availability of the various amenities in the stay. Benefit of the Four G technology had developed a system to how can reach with their destinations along with maps, hotel bookings and any other services. (Munford, 2016).

The digital apparatus is useful for the entrepreneurs as well as the travelers. With the help of digital technology customers can provide their feedback and sharing their views on the social media platform and because of this owner can maintained his quality to attract the customers. (Piccoli, 2008).

Digital transformation is the social, structural and operative modification of an association, business or ecology over a keen addition of digital technologies, procedures and capabilities across all heights and purposes in an obtainable and planned mode.

(Koutroumanis, 2011).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the effect of digitalization on entrepreneurship development.
2. To understand the development of digital business in India and globally.
3. To acknowledge the benefits and drawbacks of digital business in hospitality entrepreneurship

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper is qualitative and descriptive in nature. Primary and secondary data used. Source of survey data is used from secondary data. The study of research area is very broad and sources of data extent through multiple places. Authors try to study for analyzing the current survey data and some case studies for better results in findings research questioned framed.

A. **Hypothesis 1:** digitalization has a positive effect on entrepreneurship development

Benis (2013) has concluded that for leadership it is important to use and identify the digital business strategy to bring about transparency in gaining and accumulating sufficient information. He also emphasized that for being an effective leader one has to build adaptive capacity which includes factors like accepting new opportunities, resilience which means facing the difficulties and challenges and the ability and willingness to sacrifice and keep learning and gaining knowledge from failures, it also includes one more factor that is the ability to become optimistic. With the use of digital technology now many companies are motivating and encouraging to lead on the path of digital transformation to

beat up the competition of the customers and competitors. Leadership helps in portraying a great role by emphasizing on the customer experience, improving on the ground level operational process and building technical business models Westerman et al. (2011).

B. Hypothesis 2: Digital leadership has a positive effect on entrepreneurship development

Digital technology brings continuous changes in the functions that are performed in a business. It involves changes in the marketing activities conducted by the business, defining structures, developing technical process setups and improving the human capabilities to access and build business value. In the changing economic era it has become important to analyze and identify the various opportunities and learn the digital capabilities O'Hea (2011).

C. Hypothesis 3: Digital technology has a positive effect on entrepreneurship development

The ability or the intensity of each and every individual with respect to the level of participation and relationship management by involving the activities of the organization is said to be as the customer engagement, Vivek(2012). For customers to achieve their goals applications provide enough information and the content needed thereby providing the functional and utilitarian experience which will help the customers achieve the goals.. the main aim of using technology and engaging the customers is to relieve them from stress. Customers are functionally motivated as it helps in improving efficiency and time saving.. in a transaction through digital technology customers interact and help in building an online identity by forming a network of social benefits like friendship and support.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION POLICY FOR HOTELS

Hotel Entrepreneurs aware about certain aims a digital transformation can be achieved. Digital transformation can increase revenue, website movement, and service quality.

It can also have controlled on lower operating costs.

1. Allow direct bookings via the Internet to capture the business of small meetings.-
Using online booking software, venues can streamline the process for small meeting planners, who have an easier time handling the event's details themselves.
2. Be sure that every page on your website is optimized for mobile devices.
3. Your website should be mobile-friendly
4. Be Mobile Quality - Customers are looking at your website and your advertising emails on their phones. To begin your entrepreneurship digital transformation, develop your business website acquisition for certain outcomes.
5. Embrace collective fundamentals on your website -

To provide a memorable and easy-to-navigate experience for planners researching your venue on your website, consider adding interactive elements. If you're not sure where to start, think about what information the planner is most likely looking for and try. Consider including interactive elements on

your website to help your planner visitors learn more about your venue. (Ratten, (2014).)Use interactive elements to engage planners on your website. Include interactive features on your website to reap the benefits and to make planners more likely to remember you.

Entrepreneurs Awareness of Digital Transformation for the business

DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN HOTEL AND HOSPITALITY

Given that it has qualities that are ideal for the use of digital technology, the tourism industry is among the first to undergo the process of digital transformation. These include the fact that the tourism product is intangible and cannot be tested prior to purchase. There is a large amount of information available to help the customers in choosing, planning, buying and using a tourism product. The structure has been changed with the help of the information and the use of technology in the tourism sector which allows advancement of new opportunities and also invite risk for the shareholders.

According to Beynon et al., digital tourism is also known as the digital support system which is experience by the tourists during their visit. The concept of a business model, according to Rainhold et al., is now essential to understanding how tourism is carried out and taking future developments in tourism into consideration. There are numerous business models in the context of digital tourism.

Various stages which are related with the travel are covered and completed under the models of digital business. In the starting phase the models were used for the prior planning of the trips and visits specially when we talk about the function of reservations of the travel services. as the time evolved the consumption of the tourist services were also included. The below figure shows the various phases of the experience of the visitors and focuses on the concept of digital business model.

Figure: stage-by-stage digital business concepts for the travel experience Stages in the authors' study were modified from those in Beynon et al.

The main focus was on the making and implementing the model easy and convenient so that to make the process and the information accessible with respect to the choosing of the destination , the process of lodging and the transportation services thereby planning the trip. The support of the digital use also involves providing the digital guides, the proper maps to provide location access, involvement of social networking sites and the use on mobile apps which includes the use of video and the audio devices while providing the tourist services and information. With the use of AR which is known as

the augmented reality and the virtual reality which is known as the VR the tourism sector has expanded at an increasing rate.

The literature suggests that selecting a holiday rental is a challenging task. As a result, highly advanced business models are used by successful digital service providers to generate reservations for holiday rentals. The largest of these online communities, TripAdvisor, is acknowledged as having a substantial impact on how travelers make decisions by encouraging member-to-member information and advice exchange. User reviews of lodging establishments are one of the numerous types of user-generated content (UGC) created in online communities and are essential to the business of housing service providers. UGC is critical for other tourism businesses, just like it is for the lodging industry, and is one of the essential elements of the most successful digital world.

FIGURE: Digital Business Model,. Source: Zentner and Spremić

It is evident from the business model's presentation that it is based on a linear value chain, with suppliers and providers of tourist services on the input side, from whom the company purchases capacity at advantageous wholesale prices, and tourists on the output side, who purchase travel-related goods or packages from the company at retail prices. (Tajeddini, (2017))Due to the utilization of online channels for sales and communication and the robust technology infrastructure, this business model is compared to travel intermediaries. value chain has reduced the expansion and development of its competitors and has selected a two-sided business model.

BENEFITS OF DIGITALIZATION IN HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

1. **Building Infrastructure at Lowest Cost:** Digital businesses save money on organizational construction and development costs, which may then be invested in better digital offerings for customers. There is also a minimum amount of paperwork and other documentation. Likewise, constant connectivity in digital company contributes to improved competitive advantage.
2. **Improves the business process:** The way that digital commerce is envisioned encourages transparency, which helps organizations reduce delays, overhead expenses, and corruption. Digital business is transformed into a streamlined operational function with the application of SAP and ERP. By connecting suppliers, logistics, and delivery, company is digitally synced, allowing for easy tracking of the actual locations of business processes.
3. **Constant Innovation and Education:** Under a digital company model, fewer employees are needed, and it also helps to identify and keep the greatest people. The interchange of ideas is encouraged via communication and teamwork. Both more lenient working conditions and more advanced job prospects are simultaneously produced. Adopting new technology, like as robotics, improves competency and boosts output.
4. **Remote Data Access:** Since data is managed across different digital platforms, it is simpler to connect new clients with diverse channels. Data-driven consumer insights aid in the gathering, storing, and analysis of data. As a result, digital strategy is better planned and carried out by carefully utilizing resources, releasing updates quickly, and closely monitoring consumer online behavior. (Spremić, (pp. 25-44).)

5. Makes the business more resilient: 24/7 operations, connectivity, and improved response are all products of digitization. Employees have a flexible work-from-home culture in line with this. The addition of comfortable features improves the responsiveness, grace, and usability of digital operations. It is believed that the more digital businesses are used, the more money they will make.

DRAWBACKS OF DIGITALIZATION IN HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

1. A very competitive person: The nature of the digital business is particularly competitive because most digital businesses aim to expand their geographic reach and increase consumer loyalty. This puts unfair pressure on startups and smaller businesses, and fierce competition encourages the 'survival of the fittest' theory.
2. Over-Reliance on Technology Prior familiarity with the internet and digital devices is required. Common issues include website crashes, broken links, slow-loading pages, inactive page buttons, and other interruptions in internet operations. Numerous processes have a short lifespan, we rely too much on technology, and buying expensive equipment is costly for consumers.
3. Privacy and Security Concerns
The privacy and security of customers, clients, and organizations themselves are the most important issues in digital business. Hacking, security breaches, online fraud, breaking the law online, engaging in anti-social behavior, collecting sensitive user data and selling it to other parties are just a few examples of issues. Information about a business, client, or individual is frequently stolen, misinterpreted, and used as leverage in blackmail. (Henama, (2018))
4. Huge Investment Is Necessary: To finance a digital firm requires a lot of infrastructure, technology installation and maintenance, partnerships, legal concerns, and government permission in advance. Investments are also made in the training of staff members and the development of their skills. As a result, consumers must pay more because the price of the product or service eventually rises.

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL BUSINESS IN INDIA AND GLOBALLY

Since the first Industrial Revolution, technology has advanced significantly, hastening the growth of our society. Without a doubt, motivated by fiction. There is a fascination with humanoid robots that goes with the unknown. However, technology is not only an essential but also a fundamental component of our daily lives, and the hospitality sector is not an exception. Success, however, varies depending on a number of factors, including how well the current technology performs and how widely it is accepted. Europe in particular, which places a high priority on privacy and data protection, appears to fall behind in this area.

In order to address challenges in the hospitality sector, increased AI and robotics integration suggests that by enhancing human skill sets with technology, workers will have more time and possibilities to provide true hospitable service. Academics believe that reducing an individual's workload and emotional burden can improve organizational performance and, eventually, increase guest pleasure. Osawa et al. (2017); Kuo et al. (2016)

Companies must make sure that all parties involved in the new technologies are aware of the operational changes and the impacts on customer experiences in order to successfully integrate non-human employees into a team (Susskind & Curry, 2015). To address negative effects on the social component of the HRI, such as naming or addressing robots, social norms and values towards the robots, but also the extent of supporting the integration of the new team member, guidelines, ethical standards, and a code of conduct must be developed. Even if it's unclear how or when more advanced applications will enter our workplaces and personal lives, social robots may very likely join our community in the near future.

CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurial organizations must ensure that their clients have a wonderful understanding from the moment they begin travelling and organizing their vacation, whether it be for travel on aero planes, lodging reservations, or enjoyment on amazing cruises. No company can dodge the digital transformation. That is a requirement of the company. (Amit, (2015).)The company needed to become used to its potential established business activity model and apply it as a plan for business growth. Inconvenient transportation, hotel, and other amenities can occasionally have a detrimental effect on the tourism and hospitality sector. These industries' competitiveness has increased as a result of the digital transition, which has also encouraged the creation of new start-ups.

The business model is presented in a way that clearly states the emphasis of the linear value chain. with suppliers and providers of tourist services on the input side from whom the company purchases capacity at cost-effective wholesale prices and tourists on the output side who buy travel-related products or packages from the company at retail prices. This business model is analogous to the traditional business models of travel intermediaries because it uses online channels for sales and communication and has a strong technical backbone. With time it has become clear that the stated linear chain has a limited scope of expansion. In contrast to its main rivals, who have opted for a more scalable two-sided platform business model, it has become evident over time that it is in reality this linear value chain that has limited expansion.

REFERENCES

1. Amit, R. &. ((2015).). Crafting business architecture: The antecedents of business model design. . Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal,, 9(4), 331-350.
2. Anggadwita, G. L. ((2017).). Socio-cultural environments and emerging economy entrepreneurship: Women entrepreneurs in Indonesia. . Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies.
3. Ferreira, J. J. ((2017)). . Entrepreneurship, innovation and competitiveness: what is the connection?. . International Journal of Business and Globalisation, , 18(1), 73-95.
4. Ferreira, J. J. ((2017)). . Knowledge spillover-based strategic entrepreneurship. . International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal, , 13, 161-167.
5. Henama, U. S. ((2018)). . Disruptive entrepreneurship using Airbnb: the South African experience. . African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure, , 7(1), 1-16.
6. Huijbens, E. H. ((2019)). . Tending to destinations: Conceptualising tourism's transformative capacities. . Tourist Studies, 19(3), 279-294.
7. Ratten, V. ((2014).). Future research directions for collective entrepreneurship in developing countries: a small and medium-sized enterprise perspective. . International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business,, 22(2), 266-274.
8. Spremić, M. I. ((pp. 25-44).). Fostering innovation and value creation through ecosystems: case of digital business models and digital platforms. In Leadership, Management, and Adoption Techniques for Digital Service Innovation. IGI Global, (2020).
9. Tajeddini, K. R. ((2017)). . Female tourism entrepreneurs in Bali, Indonesia. . Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management, , 31, 52-58.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256298039_E_Hospital_Management_Hospital_Information_Systems_-_Changing_Trends
2. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIRCF06010.pdf>

3. <https://www.cigniti.com/blog/digital-transformation-hospitality-industry/>
4. <http://shura.shu.ac.uk/25422/3/Tajeddini%20Tourism%20hospitality%20and%20digital%20transformation.pdf>
5. <https://www.cihms.com/en/digital-transformation-in-the-hospitality-industry/>
6. https://repositorio.ucp.pt/bitstream/10400.14/27003/1/Dissertation_PiaMairinger.pdf
7. <https://hoteltechreport.com/news/digital-transformation>
8. <https://hospitalityinspired.sommet-education.com/news-insights/trends-hospitality/impact-digital-transformation-hospitality-industry>